

Sample Name: PA UV <1 μm

Material: Polyamide (Nylon-6,6)

Size: <1 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Structure

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- 50% particles are <1 μm
- Median diameter (D_{50v}) = 2,19 μm
- Particles have a rounded, irregular morphology
- 4,9 x10¹¹ particles per gram
- 25470 cm²/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% C₆H₁₁NO (PA) determined by XRF
- No changes due to milling or aging observed in FTIR spectrum
- Not able to obtain a cathodoluminescence spectrum

Description of terms

- D[4,3]:Volume mean (μm)
- D[3,2]:Surface area mean (μm)
- D[2,1]: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- D[1,0]: Number length mean (μm)
- D_{50v}: Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_{50N}: Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w: Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w: Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm²/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
4,35	2,07	1,44	1,16	0,94	2,19	4.9×10^{11}	25470

Chemical Bonding (Using μ -FTIR provided by TNO)Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$	99,937
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Si	74
S	11
Cl	2040
K	19
Ca	29
Ti	2
Cr	23
Mn	1
Fe	86
Ni	7
Cu	2
Zn	2
Mo	1

Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (*provided by TNO*)

Not available